

Microwave assisted one-pot synthesis of cholesterol derivatives

Bhim Prasad Pradhan, Utpal Debnath and Pranab Ghosh*

Natural Product and Polymer Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, Darjeeling-734 013, West Bengal, India

E-mail : pizy12@yahoo.com Fax : 91-353-2699001

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Abstract : Microwave induced one-pot synthesis of cholest-4-en-7 β -ol from 7-oxocholest-3,5-dien has been performed. The structure of the compound has been confirmed by spectral data (IR, NMR and Mass) and by comparison with already reported physical data.

Keywords : Cholesterol derivative, microwave, ethylenediamine.

Introduction

The conventional method¹ of reduction in presence of lithium-ethylenediamine involves large excess of hazardous, expensive, polluting organic solvents; a prolonged reaction time and tedious working procedures which also produce significant amount of side products. Thus, a one pot method involving milder, more selective, inexpensive and eco-friendly reaction condition is still in demand.

The potential application of microwave technology (MW) in organic synthesis is rapidly increasing² because of the reaction simplicity, less polluting and minimum reaction time providing rapid access to large libraries of diverse molecules. This technology has been implemented since the middle of 1980s in the field of organic chemistry. The increasing number of related publications in recent years indicate that this technique is a widely accepted unconventional energy source for performing organic syntheses due to substantial reduction in reaction time^{3,4}, better yields⁵ and easier work-up procedures⁶. In addition, the high selectivity of the reactions contributes to the prevention of waste formation. Although a very few reports of microwave assisted transformative reactions of terpenoids, steroids and flavonoids are known, reports about the microwave assisted transformative reaction of triterpenoids and steroids are still scanty⁷.

With this in mind we have attempted a microwave-assisted lithium-ethylenediamine reduction on steroidal skeleton taking 7-oxocholest-3,5-dien **2** as a model compound.

Results and discussion

Microwave-assisted organic synthesis⁸⁻¹¹ has had a profound impact on the way chemists approach organic and parallel syntheses. Clearly, reductions in reaction times, improved yields and suppression of side products, less polluting relative to traditional thermal heating, are benefits of this emerging technology. With this in mind we have attempted a microwave-assisted lithium-ethylenediamine reduction taking 7-oxocholest-3,5-dien (**2**) as a model compound.

*Reaction of lithium-ethylenediamine on cholest-3,5-dien-7-one (**2**) under microwave irradiation :*

Cholest-3,5-dien-7-one (**2**) prepared by the oxidation of 7-oxo cholesteryl acetate (**1**) with *p*-TsOH was subjected to microwave irradiation (100 W, 100 °C) for 20 min in presence of small pieces of metallic Li and dry ethylenediamine (EDA). The product obtained after usual work-up showed a single spot in TLC after usual work-up. It was purified by column chromatography followed by crystallization from a mixture of chloroform and methanol that yielded a white crystal of compound **A**, analyzed for C₂₇H₄₆O, m.p. 115–116 °C. The compound gave positive TNM test for unsaturation. The UV spectrum of the compound **A** showed no absorption above 220 nm. IR spectrum of the compound **A** showed peak at 3340 cm⁻¹ for hydroxyl functional group and the peak at 820 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of trisubstituted double bond. Mass spectrum of the compound **A** showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 386 and other peaks appeared at *m/z* 368, 353, 327, 301, 275, 213, 145, 107, 91, 55. ¹H NMR spec-

trum of **A** showed the presence of five methyls, three of which appeared as doublets at δ 0.87, 0.88, 0.93 due to three secondary methyls, each one with same coupling constant of 6.5 Hz and two as singlets at δ 0.85 and 1.29 ppm. C_4 -H proton appeared as a broad singlet at δ 5.32 ppm. The multiplet centred at δ 3.57 integrated for one proton is due to C_7 -H proton. Another peak appeared at δ 2.30 as a multiplet was due to the C_7 -OH proton. ^{13}C NMR accounted for all 27 carbons. C_4 and C_5 carbon atoms appeared at 125.46 ppm as a doublet and 143.49 ppm as a singlet respectively. C_7 carbon appeared at 73.4 ppm due to its attachment with -OH group. On the basis of the above analysis compound **A** was identified as cholest-4(5)-en-7 β -ol¹² (**3**).

cal shifts in δ , ppm; TMS as internal standard) and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in $CDCl_3$ on Bruker Avance 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer. Optical rotation was measured on a JASCO DIP-4 digital polarimeter on chloroform solution. IR spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer using KBr discs; UV spectra in methanol on Shimadzu UV-240 spectrometer; mass spectra in Varian MAT 711 instrument at 70 eV. All the chemicals were of AR grade (from Merck, Fluka, SRL) and were purified prior to their use following the standard protocols. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (BDH 60–120 mesh). TLC was performed over silica gel G.

Discussion of the reaction mechanism :

The formation of product cholest-4(5)-en-7 β -ol (**3**) from cholest-3,5-dien-7-one (**2**) suggest that under the highly basic condition the reaction involved is a Li-ethylenediamine reduction, i.e. a typical Benkeser reduction of an enone system to alcohol. 7-Oxocholesteryl acetate (**1**) undergoes deacetoxylation forming cholest-3,5-dien-7-one (**2**) which ultimately forms cholest-4(5)-en-7 β -ol (**3**). A schematic presentation of the mechanism is given below in the Scheme 1 for the reduction of ketones with extended double bonds.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary method and were uncorrected. 1H NMR spectra (chemi-

Reaction of 7-oxocholesteryl acetate (**1**) with *p*-toluene sulphonic acid :

A solution of 7-oxocholesteryl acetate (**1**) (0.5 g) in toluene (15 mL) containing *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (0.5 g) was heated under reflux in a nitrogen atmosphere for 7 h. The solution was then cooled, diluted and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed successively with water and dilute sodium carbonate solution and again with water till neutral and then dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation of ether gave a solid residue (0.3 g) which on crystallization from ethanol afforded crystals of cholest-3,5-dien-7-one¹³ (**2**) m.p. 112–114 °C, identical with an authentic sample of cholest-3,5-dien-7-one.

Lithium-ethylenediamine reduction of cholest-3,5-dien-7-one (**2**) under microwave irradiation :

All the microwave reactions were carried out in a 10

Scheme 1

mL sealed glass tubes in a focused mono-mode microwave oven ("Discover" by CEM Corporation, Matthews, NC) at 100 W (100 °C) in only 20 min reaction time. A solution of the compound **B** (0.0013 mol) in dry ethylene diamine was taken in a 10 mL sealed tube. Small pieces of lithium metal (0.01 mol) were added to a solution of 7-cholest-3,5-dien-7-one (**2**). The reaction mixture was then irradiated under microwave. It was then cooled and treated with solid NH_4Cl to destroy excess of lithium, acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with water till neutral and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation of the solvent (ether) furnished a residue which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel followed by crystallization from a mixture of chloroform-methanol to afford colourless

crystals of compound **A**; its mol. formula $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}$, m.p. 115–116 °C [Lit.¹² m.p 116 °C], $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 21.4^\circ$; IR : 3340 cm^{-1} (-OH), 820 cm^{-1} ; TNM test : Positive; MS : m/z 386, 368, 353, 327, 301, 275, 213, 145, 107, 91, 55; ^1H NMR : δ 0.85, 1.29 (6H, s, $2 \times t\text{-Me}$), δ 0.87, 0.88, 0.93 (d, $3 \times \text{sec-Me}$, J 6.5 Hz), δ 5.32 (C4-H), δ 3.57 (C7-H), δ 2.30 (C7-OH); ^{13}C NMR : C4 (125.5), C5 (143.5) and C7 (73.4).

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